

THE SUBSTANTIVE AND OBJECTIVE ASPECT OF THE FORMATION OF STRATEGIES FOR MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TOURIST TERMINOLOGY AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article discusses the substantive and objective aspect of the formation of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology among undergraduate students. The author notes the purpose of the proposed methodology as the formation and improvement of foreign language communicative competence of students in the tourism sector, relying on strategies for mastering foreign language professional terminology.

Keywords: linguistic, sociocultural, strategic, social, sociolinguistic, thematic, intercultural competencies, day spa, kids club, information center, police.

Consideration of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology provides for their close relationship with all components of the training system: the purpose, content, principles, methods and means of training. The Model Program on a Foreign Language for Non-Language Higher Education Institutions states that knowledge of a foreign language is an integral component of the professional training of all specialists at a university, the study of a foreign language is aimed at the comprehensive development of communicative, cognitive, informational, sociocultural, professional and general cultural competencies students. The main goal of teaching a foreign language is formulated as students mastering the necessary and sufficient level of communicative competence to solve social and communicative problems in various fields of everyday, cultural, professional and scientific activities when communicating with foreign partners, as well as for further self-education [1, p.34-39].

Based on the analyzed documents, we determine the purpose of the proposed methodology as the formation and improvement of foreign language communicative competence of students in the tourism sector, relying on strategies for mastering foreign language professional terminology.

Linguistic competence is the possession of knowledge about the language system, about the rules by which language unit function in speech [2, p.448], as well as the ability and willingness to interpret and produce meaningful statements constructed in accordance with the norms of the language. Working with texts from the tourism sphere of communication allows students to master the professional vocabulary of the tourism industry, decoding abbreviations (LHR - London Heathrow airport, NSW - New South Wales, RBG - The Royal Botanic Gardens), understanding abbreviations (2A + 2Ch - 2 adults and 2 children; NA - not available, pc - pieces), units (sq km, km / hr, oz, lb) and compound words (half-board, holiday farmhouse,

theme park) [3, p.44-50]. Possession of tourist discourse treatment strategies enables students to bring into the system knowledge of the rules for the functioning of language tools, and provides the opportunity to make an informed choice of language tools from the existing "repertoire" depending on the communication situation. Strategies optimize the acquisition of language knowledge, as activate attention, memory, thinking of students. The presence of strategies for mastering a foreign language tourist discourse in the students' speech experience provides the processes for creating speech works that meet the requirements of lexical and grammatical connectivity, meaningful logic, and organizing statements based on professionally significant texts [4, p.148]

Sociocultural competence implies the ability and willingness to use in the course of communication knowledge of the national and cultural features of the social and speech behavior of the speakers of the studied language: customs, etiquette, social stereotypes, history, culture [2, p.448]. In the process of reading professionally oriented texts selected by us, students get acquainted with sociocultural reality, presented not only verbally, but also iconically and paraverbally, learn to decode, understand, transmit information recorded in a symbolic sign system inherent in the English-

speaking culture, for example -

kids club, - Police. The role of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology in the formation and improvement of sociocultural competence is related to the fact that they control the processes of understanding, processing and using information contained in the texts of the tourist sphere of communication, including information of a sociocultural nature. In relation to the strategy being considered, it can be assumed that they increase the students' ability to "sociocultural self-education" by working with the terminological sphere of tourism, saturated

with socio-cultural facts. The obtained sociocultural information can be used to satisfy tourist information requests, and can also serve as a basis for students to analyze situations of professional communication, a conscious choice of culturally acceptable forms of interaction [5, p.446] with clients in intercultural settings communication. Thus, the presence of strategies ensures the creation of a discourse in accordance with the sociocultural context and sociocultural characteristics of the addressee.

Strategic competence is understood in a number of works as the ability to use verbal and nonverbal strategies to compensate for insufficient language skills, gaps in the speech and social experience of communication in a foreign language environment, and to overcome communication difficulties. However, we believe that strategic competence is not limited to compensatory techniques, but includes training methods and tactics that ensure the student's autonomy [6, p.128].

Intercultural competence implies the ability to communicate with representatives of other cultures, to accept and understand their differences, moving away from negative attitudes (prejudice, aggression); compare and make judgments, adequately perceive and evaluate the situation of communication, use precisely those verbal, paraverbal and nonverbal means that correspond to communicative intentions and promote communicative interaction, the criterion of which is adequate feedback. In relation to the conditions of a non-linguistic university, we are talking about the formation of students' ability and willingness to participate in intercultural professional communication, otherwise, the formation of intercultural professional communicative competence within the limits limited by the needs of the future professional and educational context [3, p.44-50].

The development of intercultural competence among students of a non-linguistic higher education institution as applied to the professional sphere of its functioning during the formation of strategies for mastering foreign-language tourist terminology predetermines their assimilation of the following knowledge and skills: knowledge of the characteristics of a tourist vocabulary in their native and English-language linguistic cultures; knowledge of structural and substantial differences in the genres of tourist monologic speech of one's own and studied cultures; the ability to compare the features of tourist terminology in two linguistic cultures; the ability to adequately apply the knowledge gained about the specifics of tourism discourse in native and other linguistic culture when generating professionally significant oral genres [7, p.432]. The development of intercultural competence of future tourism bachelors in the course of focused work on the formation of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology is associated with the establishment of such qualities as the ability to reconsider the established professional views and stereotypes inherent in their own tourist culture, to show cultural sensitivity and tolerance towards to intercultural differences [8, p.18].

Having analyzed the points of view of different authors on the component composition of the content

of training and taking into account the specifics of our research, we single out the following components in the content of the training on the formation of strategies for mastering foreign-language tourist discus: 1) extralinguistic components: areas of communication, topics, situations of communication; 2) written texts of the tourist sphere of communication; 3) communicative goals and intentions; 4) language material; 5) knowledge; 6) strategies for mastering foreign tourist discourse; 7) skills that implement strategies for mastering foreign tourism discourse; 8) emotional and evaluative component [9, p.89-93].

Areas of communication, we define as "an extralinguistic background that affects speech behavior and the choice of language means" [10, p.216]. In the formation of strategies for mastering tourism terminology, communication areas should be selected in accordance with the field of professional activity of the tourism industry employee.

Based on the analysis of the educational complex of the discipline "Business in Tourism and Hospitality in English", authentic textbooks for students of tourism, we selected and arranged the following topics in a logical sequence: 1) Travel agencies; 2) Dealing with guests; 3) Tourist Information Centers; 4) Welcome to our restaurant!; 5) Guided tours.

Acquaintance involves showing and explaining material that is aimed at encouraging students to think. When forming strategies for mastering a foreign language tourist discourse, the demonstration takes place in the form of a demonstration to students of actions to process a verbal text for its subsequent presentation, for example, highlighting keywords, using the Text Mapping Plus, Time Line, Magnet Summary Organizer techniques. Acquaintance includes presenting to students the means of cohesion of discourse and speech cliches necessary for creating genres of tourist terminology [5, p.446]. When explaining to students, the essence of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology and their skills is revealed; information is provided on the parameters of the genres of foreign tourist discourse, the qualities of oral English-language discourse. The teacher also organizes an independent study by students of the material set forth in our manual "The world through the eyes of tourists".

The training organization method is aimed at creating conditions for the multiple and conscious execution of individual actions in the framework of educational and special speech situations. In the framework of our study, this method is aimed at developing the skills of using speech cliches, strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology [11, p.324]. So, when forming strategies for the modification of creolized texts, students learn to analyze information, work with individual elements of the text: headline, photographs (illustrations), slogan, verbal part. On various creolized texts (menus, brochures, maps), students train in explaining acronyms, abbreviations, matching synonyms and definitions for given words. In subsequent exercises, a gradual complication of the task is provided [7, p.432].

The method of organizing the application in our research involves creating a context in which students

can practice using strategies for modifying a foreign language professional terminology [10, p.216]. So, students need to complete assignments for the content of professional texts: for example, compose a tour text, select a hotel according to the specified requirements, explain the route on the map. In addition, within the framework of students in whom they are studying, playing the role of a tourist, people or communicative intentions work.

Students individual work. Students are encouraged to study the contents of the texts of tourist websites, authentic electronic brochures in order to collect the necessary information to compose an individual text for the excursion, create an advertising speech, a message about attractions (tourist products, tourist services, events) [6, p.128].

The excursion method finds application in the excursion process, where the comprehensive method of cognition is widely used, which makes it possible to choose from the observed objects the most important, significant, excitingly obtained material with your experience and knowledge [1, p.34-39]. The essence of the excursion method is determined by two interrelated conditions: local (the study of objects is carried out at their location) and motor (the study is in connection with movement in space).

The implementation of the excursion method in our research involves the organization of excursions, the constituent parts of which are a story and a show, in real time with visits to historical and cultural objects and in online mode (virtual tours) with immersion in an inocultural environment [9, p.89-93]. The organization of excursions should be built from simple to complex, from familiar to unfamiliar, from natural to artificial, from real to virtual and includes the following steps: preparation (discussion of a topic, route, drawing up a work plan, collecting information), the actual tour (demonstration of the prepared excursion, activation by the teacher of the students' independence and research activities based on the emotional and sensory experience gained in communicating with the excursion objects), discussion of the excursion [10, p.216]. Using the excursion method allows you to build the ability of students to create foreign language tourist terminology, develop skills and research activities, teamwork, and also enhances interest in future professional activities, as a result of which there is an in-depth and lasting assimilation of the material.

Portfolio Method. A portfolio in the general sense is the collection, analysis and evaluation of samples and products of educational and cognitive activities of students and relevant information materials [8, p.18]. The portfolio for students is the organizer of their educational and professional, scientific, research, creative, social work, technology and a place for collecting materials, analyzing information, a tool for self-assessment, reflection and self-improvement [11, p.324].

The portfolio method is implemented in the formation of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology in the accumulation, systematization of training, and subsequently workers in the tourism industry, artifacts, texts, books, videos needed to

create genres of tourist terminology, as well as educational and cognitive products (professional, research) activities. Portfolio, as a materialized form of demonstration of achievements, can be presented in paper, electronic or online versions. Using the portfolio method generates research abilities, develops students' autonomy, allows them to improve their professional competence, reflect and self-evaluate their own work, as well as "construct their own knowledge, develop the ability to independently think and act" [11, p.324].

In our research, the project method is implemented in the creation of tourism projects, excursions, advertising speeches, greetings individually and in groups by students in a foreign language class. They can be attributed to constructive-practical, role-based, as well as information and research types of projects. These projects may be devoted to studying the country of the language being studied, a specific region, and places popular with tourists. The project method provides a link between the process of mastering foreign tourist discourse and the assimilation of subject knowledge in tourism and creates the conditions for the real application of this knowledge [6, p.128].

The next component of the methodological system is teaching tools, to which we include authentic texts of the tourist sphere of communication, professional foreign-language sites. However, the key tool for teaching strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology is the developed training manual "The world through the eyes of tourists" [11, p.324].

The purpose of the manual is to teach students the strategies for presenting information extracted from tourist texts, as well as the creation of oral statements based on these texts.

Thus, in this section, we have described the substantively targeted aspect of the methodology for the formation of strategies for mastering foreign language tourist terminology. The purpose of teaching the proposed methodology is the formation and improvement of foreign-language communicative competence, in the unity of all its components of linguistic, sociocultural, discursive, strategic, social, sociolinguistic, thematic, intercultural, based on the strategy of mastering foreign-language professional terminology. The manual is intended for students studying the tourism business, for students of lyceums, gymnasiums and higher educational institutions, where the program provides for the study of a business foreign language.

References

1. Kismetova G.N., Bismanova Z.Y. Modeling Foreign language professional activities Tourism in the learning environment of a non-linguistic university (article). Naukova mysl informacyjnej powieki www.rusnauka.com. Przemysl, Poland 07-15 March 2019, P. 34-39.
2. Азимов Э. Г. Новый словарь методических терминов и понятий (теория и практика обучения языкам): Словарь / Э. Г. Азимов, А. Н. Щукин. – М.: ИКАР, 2010. – 448 с.
3. Аликина Е. Ю. Атриктивная функция метафоры в туристском дискурсе / Е. Ю. Аликина С. Л. Мишланова // Вестник Пермского университета.

Российская и зарубежная филология. – 2010. - № 6. – С. 44-50.

4 Алилуйко Е. А. Формирование коммуникативной компетентности менеджеров туризма в процессе изучения иностранного языка: дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.08 / Е. А. Алилуйко. – М., 2000. – 148 с.

5 Алмазова Н. И. Когнитивные аспекты формирования межкультурной компетентности при обучении иностранному языку в неязыковом вузе: дис. ... д-ра пед. наук: 13.00.02 / Н. И. Алмазова. – СПб., 2003. – 446 с.

6 Анисимова Е. Е. Лингвистика текста и межкультурная коммуникация (на материале креолизованных текстов): учеб. пособие / Е. Е. Анисимова. – М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2003. – 128 с.

7 Анисимова Т. В. Современная деловая риторика: учеб. пособие / Т. В. Анисимова, Е. Г. Гимпельсон. - М.: МПСИ, 2004. - 432 с.

8 Антюшина М. О. Обучение иноязычной профессиональной речи будущего учителя иностранного языка в процессе профессиональной подготовки: автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.02 / М. О. Антюшина. – Пенза, 2006. – 18 с.

9 Апальков В. Г. Компонентный состав межкультурной компетенции / В. Г. Апальков, П. В. Сысоев // Вестник Тамбовского ун-та. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. - 2008. - №8. - С. 89-93.

10 Архипова Ю. В. Методика формирования речемыслительных стратегий студентов на основе предъявления тексто-графической информации: Английский язык, неязыковое среднее специальное учебное заведение: дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.02 / Ю. В. Архипова. – Тамбов, 2005. – 216 с.

11 Астафурова Т. Н. Стратегии коммуникативного поведения в профессионально-значимых ситуациях межкультурного общения (лингвистический и дидактический аспекты): дис. ... д-ра пед. наук: 13.00.02, 10.02.19 / Т. Н. Астафурова. – М., 1997. – 324 с.